

RES4LIVE

ENERGY SMART LIVESTOCK FARMING
TOWARDS ZERO FOSSIL FUEL CONSUMPTION

Report with the results obtained on energy and production performances of RES and energy efficiency solutions

Deliverable 4.3

WP4. Implementation and testing of the solutions in pilot farms

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ABBREVIATIONS

BHE	:	Borehole Heat Exchanger
BTES	:	Borehole Thermal Energy Storage
CHP	:	Combined Heat and Power
COP	:	Coefficient of Performance
CNG	:	Compressed Natural Gas
DSHP	:	Dual Source Heat Pump
HEX	:	Heat Exchanger
HP	:	Heat Pump
HTF	:	Heat Transfer Fluid
HVAC	:	Heating, Ventilation And Air Conditioning
LPG	:	Liquid Petroleum Gas
PVT	:	Photovoltaic Thermal
RES	:	Renewable Energy System
SCOP	:	Seasonal Coefficient Of Performance
SPF	:	Seasonal Performance Factor
THI	:	Temperature-Humidity-Index
TRT	:	Thermal Response Test
UMTS	:	Universal Mobile Telecommunications System

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UNIBO – UNIVERSITY OF BOLOGNA

ATB - LEIBNIZ INSTITUTE FOR AGRICULTURAL ENGINEERING AND BIOECONOMY

EV ILVO - RESEARCH INSTITUTE FOR AGRICULTURE, FISHERIES AND FOOD

UGENT - GHENT UNIVERSITY

CERTH - CENTRE FOR RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY-HELLAS

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MG SUSTAINABLE - MG SUSTAINABLE ENGINEERING AB

CETRI - CENTER FOR TECHNOLOGY RESEARCH & INNOVATION LTD

GOLINELLI - GOLINELLI GIULIO

EAAP - FEDERAZIONE EUROPEA PER LA ZOOTECNICA

EUREC - EUREC EESV

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The aim of the H2020 project RES4LIVE lies in the development and testing of efficient and economically feasible renewable energy systems (RES) to de-fossilize various kinds of livestock operations.

WP4 focuses on the implementation and testing of solutions in pilot farms. Previous deliverables, D4.1 and D4.2, covered the design and preparation of these solutions, followed by their installation on the pilot farms. This final deliverable, D4.3, presents the outcomes from monitoring the interventions, specifically their performance and efficiency. After a brief introduction, the report is structured around the four pilot farms, detailing key metrics for each intervention. The findings from this deliverable contribute to subsequent Tasks in other work packages, such as T5.1 (Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform) and T6.5 (Inventory of best practices of RES4LIVE in livestock farms). The report concludes with a summary of WP4's key findings.

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1 INTRODUCTION

This section of the RES4LIVE project aims to present the results from monitoring the interventions implemented across the four pilot farms, with a focus on evaluating their performance and effectiveness in terms of energy savings and the substitution of fossil fuels with renewable energy sources.

The report provides a comprehensive review of all RES interventions deployed by the pilot farms, analysing their impact and identifying any challenges encountered during the monitoring and testing phases. Additionally, it assesses the extent to which these interventions met their intended energy goals and highlights any technical or operational issues that may affect scalability or broader application.

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2 TESTING AND MONITORING OF THE INSTALLED SOLUTIONS IN THE EV ILVO FARM

2.1 PVT and solar station system

2.1.1 Overview

Figure 1 (A) shows a simplified schematic overview of the installed renewable energy technologies at EV-ILVO. The main components are 24 hybrid solar panels on the roof Figure 1 (C), a solar control system Figure 1 (B), two modular heat pumps of 30 kW each, and an 800-liter thermal energy storage tank. In the above, the red and blue lines represent supply and return pipelines, respectively. The solid lines show passage lines for the 35 % glycol solution whereas the dotted lines indicate water pipes. The main measurement points and quantities are shown inside pink borders, and TS indicates the temperature sensor.

The heat transfer fluid is a 35% glycol solution heated up in solar hybrid panels and stores the energy in the thermal storage tank. The two modular heat pumps – a high and a medium temperature heat pump - raise the temperature of the water that will be circulating in the domestic hot water, air heaters and floor heater circuits of the pig farm. The thermal energy stored in the tank will be a source for the heat pumps to increase the COP. On the other hand, the electricity produced is connected to an internal power line of the farm for direct self-consumption.

The hybrid solar collector panels used in the ILVO pig farm are Apora aH72SK panels (Apora, Zaragoza, Spain). They are flat plate PVT thermal collectors with Mono-crystalline. This model is capable of generating a peak electrical power of 350 W with a module-rated efficiency of 17.8 % and 1,200 W of thermal power. The hybrid solar collector system consists of 24 collectors installed as four groups of six panels, resulting in a total aperture area of 45.12 m² on the roof of the pig farm. The PVT system has an installed electrical and thermal capacity of 8.4 kW_{electrical} and 28.8 kW_{thermal}, respectively. The PVTs are connected to an inverter (FIMER, Milano, Italy) on the farm for electricity supply directly to the farm.

The solar station is the main pumping system to transfer heat from the solar thermal collectors to the end user. The solar station used was designed by MG Sustainable Engineering AB (Sweden) to standardize solar stations for mid-size PVT applications such as livestock farms. It was manufactured by KEterm AB in Sweden. The pump transfers heat from the solar field to the solar station heat exchanger, and an intermediate circuit transfers heat from the heat exchanger to the storage tank through another pump. Heat stored in the storage tank is used by the heat pumps to deliver the final heat to the farm.

The control system used is a RESOL MX solar controller with a RESOL DL2 data logger, which communicates data in real-time to a server. The control algorithm was developed by MG Sustainable engineering. The controller activates the solar circuit pump as soon as the solar collectors are hotter than the tank, or if solar irradiance is above a threshold (> 200 Wm⁻² for 60 s). There are two heat flow meters; one for the heat delivered from the solar collectors to the solar station and one for the heat delivered to the tank. The pumps are not operated at variable speed and the flow rate in the solar circuit is ca. 30 L min⁻¹.

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Figure 1. (A) Schematic overview of the installed solar-thermal system, (B) picture of the installed solar control system and (C) picture of the installed hybrid solar panels on the roof of the pig farm at ILVO.

2.1.2 Solar irradiance

Figure 2 shows the solar irradiance data from July 2023 to March 2024 as a carpet plot. In four months, July, August, September and October more than 1000 W m⁻² insolation was recorded. The maximum solar irradiance recorded was 350 W m⁻² in December 2023.

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Figure 2. Daily evolution of solar Irradiance levels ($W m^{-2}$) from July 2023 to March 2024 as recorded by the solar irradiance sensor.

2.1.3 Thermal performance analysis

Solar energy increases the temperature of HTF, and the amount of heat transferred (Q) in kilowatts (kW) to it can then be calculated using Equation (1) given below.

$$Q = \dot{m}C_p\Delta T \quad (1)$$

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Where $\dot{m} [kg s^{-1}]$ is the mass flow rate of the heat transfer fluid (HTF) measured by flow sensors, $C_p [\frac{J}{kg K}]$ is the specific heat capacity of the glycol-water mixture at constant pressure, and $\Delta T [K]$ is the temperature difference between the hot and cold sides of the system solar collector. Note that the value of C_p of propylene glycol, which is the HTF, is estimated using the weighted average method considering 65 % water and 35 % propylene glycol. The c_p and density of the glycol-water mixture are found to be $3,491 \frac{J}{kg K}$ and $1,039 \frac{kg}{m^3}$.

Figure 3 shows the daily amount of thermal energy produced by the hybrid solar system during the measurement period from July 2023 to March 2024. The solar irradiance values integrated over time for each day are also shown as blue bars in Figure 3. There were days when the daily thermal energy production was higher than 100 kWh in the months of July, early August and September (early September). On the contrary, negligible heat generation is recorded in the months of December 2023 and January 2024. The produced thermal energy is as expected directly correlated to the respective solar insolation data. Higher solar insolation corresponds with the higher thermal energy produced and conversely, low thermal energy output corresponds to low insolation. During August 2023, the thermal energy production was nearly consistent, except for some days at the end of the month that were cloudy.

Figure 3. Daily thermal energy production (red bars) and solar insolation (blue bars) from July 2023 and March 2024.

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2.1.4 Electrical performance analysis

Figure 4 shows the daily amount of electrical energy produced by the hybrid solar system during the measurement period from October 2023 to February 2024. There were days when the daily electrical energy production was not recorded as the integrated system was on performance tests. Likewise, the heat energy production and the electrical energy production of the hybrid solar system vary in relation to the solar insolation.

Figure 4. Daily electrical energy production (green bars) and insolation (blue bars) from October 2023 and February 2024.

The daily electrical energy production shown in green bars on the figure and described in the preceding paragraph is AC power after the inversion. Here we have added the plots of the AC and DC power (Figure 5) generated and the difference between them which is attributed to losses in the inverter (Figure 6). The maximum power lost in the inverter unit is around 180 W and the mean loss of power in the inverter is 20 W.

Figure 5: Electrical power AC (top) and DC (bottom) production from October '23 and February '24.

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Figure 6: The difference between AC and DC powers from October '23 and February '24.

2.1.5 Electrical & thermal performance combined

Table 1 summarizes the amount of average thermal and electrical energy produced by the hybrid solar system during the measurement period from July 2023 to March 2024 per day. During the seven consecutive months, the hybrid solar system generated around 4.5 MWh of thermal energy. In the five consecutive months from October to February, the installed hybrid solar system produced around 2.3 MWh of electrical energy. The month of December 2023 has days with the lowest thermal and electrical energy production that corresponds with its lowest solar isolation.

Table 1. Daily average thermal and electrical energy generated in each of the measurement months with respect to the solar isolation.

Month	Daily average Thermal energy generated [kWh]	Daily average Electrical energy generated [kWh]	Daily average Insolation [kWh]
July	72	-	504
August	51	-	465
September	52	-	434
October	16	25	213
November	6	14	82
December	0	7	44
January	10	14	87
February	13	19	115
March	41	23	275

2.2 Heat pumps

The high-temperature heat pump (40 kW) always maintains a set point of 60 °C to provide sanitary hot water and air heating. The low-temperature heat pump (25 kW), with a set point temperature of 42 °C, is connected only to the underfloor heating system used for piglets.

The division into two heat pumps should be beneficial to the efficiency of the system as compared to the original installation. Originally, a natural gas boiler provided water at 70 °C for everything and was cooled down to 42 °C for underfloor heating, losing valuable heat in the process.

When the temperature of the thermal storage tank (TES) is above 37 °C, the heat pumps will start operating in a water-water regime until the temperature drops below 17 °C. Otherwise, the dry

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cooler serves as a heat source for the heat pumps using either one or two fans, depending on the heat demand, thus operating in an air-water regime.

2.2.1 Test run from 28/11/2023 to 01/12/2023

During the first test run, some of the logging data was mislabelled and some debugging had to be done in the logging system had to be performed (Figure 7). Therefore, we do not have accurate data yet, as can be seen in the power consumption and heating capacity. Eventually, the system had to be shut down because of a faulty resistor. Temperatures inside the thermal storage tank reached below -8 °C when the outside temperature dropped to below 0 °C. This resistor was replaced end of January.

Figure 7. Test run results from 28/11/2023 to 01/12/2023 in EV ILVO pilot farm.

2.2.2 Test run from 29/01/2024 to 07/02/2024

This run had to be shut down due to the fuse tripping. We found out that the defrost cycle, using the electrical resistor, cannot run in parallel with the heat pumps. By the end of 2024, ILVO should have upgraded its electricity network which should make it feasible to operate both at the same time (Figure 8). For now, we have implemented to use of the boiler as a back-up system. It should automatically turn on when a defrost cycle is being performed.

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Figure 8. Test run results from 29/01/2024 to 07/02/2024 in EV ILVO pilot farm.

2.2.3 Test run from 07/03/2024 to 19/03/2024

Everything working as planned, although less efficiently than expected. Most of the time, the heat pump has to run in the air-water regime through the dry cooler. When it switches to water-water the dry cooler – off, a fast dip can be seen in the temperature of the storage tank. There could be a more efficient operation strategy (Figure 9). The test run was shut down due to noise complaints. The office space of the pig farm is located next to the heat pump system. By the 6th of May, the placement of sound isolation inside the installation room and around the compressors was finished.

Figure 9. Test run results from 07/03/2024 to 19/03/2024 in EV ILVO pilot farm.

2.2.4 Test run from 07/05/2024 to 29/05/2024

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The system is running as intended. The heat pump system can operate longer times in water-water modus, as solar irradiance increases (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Test run results from 07/05/2024 to 29/05/2024 in EV ILVO pilot farm.

The low-temperature heat pump might be a bit oversized, operating at a lower compressor capacity, which negatively influences the part load ratio of the heat pump (Figure 11). The high-temperature heat pump performs well but continuously has to go into ON/OFF mode.

Figure 11. Compressors' capacity in EV ILVO pilot farm.

For the COP calculation (Figure 12):

- Heat capacity / Power consumption if the power consumption != 0
- removed 3 outliers for the low-temperature HP who were above 100

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Figure 12. Heat pumps' COP calculations in EV ILVO pilot farm.

The average COP of the high-temperature heat pump is 3.07 and for the low-temperature heat pump 5.25 during this test run.

2.3 Sensors and smart control

The upgraded sensor and smart control system at the EV ILVO pig farm are shown in Figure 13. The sensor system includes temperature (Pt1000), relative humidity, carbon dioxide (CO₂) and ammonia (NH₃) sensors. The environmental condition inside the farm has been monitored since April 2023, and some of the data from the sensors is shown in Figure 14.

Figure 13. Sensor and control system installed at EV-ILVO pig farm T°, RH, CO₂ and NH₃ sensors and floor plan with installation location.

Figure 14. Environment measurement data from the new sensor system from April to the end of September 2023 inside the pig fattening compartment.

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3 TESTING AND MONITORING OF THE INSTALLED SOLUTIONS IN THE GOLINELLI FARM

3.1 PVT system and solar station

The Golinelli swine farm (GOLI) is located in Mirandola, in the province of Modena (northern Italy), and rears 500 sows and 2,500 weaners. The farm consists of a farrowing barn, a nursery barn, a gestation barn, and a hog barn with a gestation sector. Before the replacement with the PVT-BTES-HP system, heating was provided by two heat pumps of 59.7 kW and 29.9 kW thermal lamps in the farrowing barn, a 34 kW LPG boiler, and 40 thermal lights in the nursery barn, and a diesel boiler in the hog barn. Cooling is achieved by evaporative cooling in the farrowing barn and gestation barn. The core objective of the RES4LIVE project was to de-fossilize the livestock agriculture industry by demonstrating technologies in various pilot farms. The goal of the project was to provide renewable heating and electricity for the nursery barn (identified as Building 16) and potentially reduce the fossil fuel consumption of the LPG boiler (approximately 7,500 kg a⁻¹) that supplies it. To achieve this, a 35 kW water-to-water heat pump (HP) was installed on the premises. Furthermore, a PVT system was installed.

Figure 15 (a) shows the aerial view of the PVT collectors installed in Building 16 of the farm. To best design the PVT system and decide on the PVT technology to be used in the farm, the heating demands of the farm were estimated from the available data. There was no demand for space heating from June to September. The renewable energy technology system to be installed (Figure 15 (b)) during the project comprises a PVT system, a borehole thermal energy storage system (BTES), and a 35 kW heat pump. The higher the temperature that the PVT system could provide to the operating fluid, the more thermal energy would be available to increase the coefficient of performance (COP) of the heat pump. The BTES would act as a seasonal heat store to cover the winter months as much as possible.

Figure 15. (a) Aerial view of the PVT collectors installed in Building 16 and (b) schematic representation of the installed PVT-BTES-HP system in the farm.

The overall system development considered three main pillars: cost-effectiveness, seamless integration with farm processes, and potential for replication. Based on data collected to estimate

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the farm's energy needs, a renewable energy system comprising PVT collectors, and a seasonal heat storage system coupled with a heat pump was designed, implemented, and is now fully operational in GOLI.

The PVT collector chosen for the GOLI farm was the Samster-SunPro 320 W monocrystalline model from Samster AB in Sweden. This model was capable of generating a maximum power of 320 W with an efficiency of 19.55 %. A thermal absorber of 1.64 m² is located beneath the photovoltaic module. The PVT system consists of 24 PVT collectors arranged in a single row on the roof, resulting in a total aperture area of 39.3 m² on the roof of the nursery barn. These collectors can provide a total of 25 kW_{th} and 7.68 kW_{el} peak power, providing thermal energy to the BTES and electricity for HP operation and the electrical needs of the nursery barn. The collectors were hydraulically distributed in four rows, each containing six of them. Nevertheless, each row was designed to have the same volumetric flow of 400 L h⁻¹. The pressure drop across one collector was estimated to be 10 kPa. Figure 16 illustrates the schematic representation of the installed RES that shows the technical specifications of various subsystems. The specifications of the installed PVT system are given in Table 2.

The PVT system was designed to use the thermal energy of the collectors to heat the heat transfer fluid (HTF). The heated operating fluid (a mixture of water and antifreeze glycol with a concentration of 35 %) was then directed to the borehole thermal energy storage (BTES) using U-pipes, where the heat would be stored in the shallow sandy aquifer. Another set of U-pipes was present in the BTES to transfer the heat stored to the cold side of the HP (35 kW). The system flow rate and control were designed so that the thermal part of the collector was capable of increasing the temperature of the HTF up to 40 °C under a maximum operating pressure of 6 bar. The flow rate of the system was set to 1 L min⁻¹ for each m² to achieve nearly 39 L min⁻¹ for the entire solar circuit.

The PVT system and solar station (balance of the plant) were designed to achieve a standardized configuration scheme that could be replicated in other applications with similar operational requirements. Thus, the solar central was explicitly made for this project (Figure 16).

Figure 16. Schematic representation of the installed RES indicating the technical specifications.

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Table 2. Total capacity (thermal and electrical) of the installed system.

Total aperture area	39.3 m ²
Total electrical capacity of the installation	7.68 kW _{el}
Maximum circuit voltage	797 V
Maximum circuit current	9.64 A
Total thermal capacity of the installation	25 kW _{th}
Flow rate in the thermal circuit	39 l/min

The performance of the PVT system is essential to understand its effectiveness and potential benefits for the swine farm and to expand its utilization to other potential sectors. The electrical energy generated from the PVT collectors is used to power the heat pump and cover the barn's partial electricity needs, while the thermal energy is stored in a BTES system and used when needed. Since there are two forms of energy generation (heat and electricity) in the system, the analysis is done separately for heat generation and electricity.

3.1.1 Heat production analysis

On a sunny day, when the irradiance exceeds the threshold and the required operational criteria are met, the HTF is directed into the cold side of the PVT collectors. Solar energy is used to increase the temperature of HTF, which in turn produces an elevated fluid temperature on the hot side of the collector field (TT02). The amount of heat transferred (Q) in kilowatts (kW) to the HTF can then be calculated using Equation (2) given below.

$$Q = \dot{m}cp\Delta T \quad (2)$$

where \dot{m} is the mass flow rate in kg s⁻¹ whose value is obtained from the flowmeter, cp is the heat capacity of the HTF at constant pressure in J kgK⁻¹, and ΔT is the temperature difference between the hot and cold sides of the PVT collector field in K. Table 3 shows the parametric values of the mixing fluids (water and glycol) used for estimating the properties of system fluid. Based on Eq. (3) and the quantities in Table 3, the cp and ρ of the system fluid are found to be 3490.9 J/kgK and 1038.5 kg/m³.

Table 3. Quantities used for the estimation of system fluid parameters.

	Propylene glycol	Water
Mix percentage (w_i)	35 %	65 %
Specific heat, cp [J/kg K] (x_i)	2,200	4,186

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	Propylene glycol	Water
Density, ρ at 25 °C [kg/m ³] (<i>xi</i>)	1,110	1,000

The field data post-installation from the farm has been collected, and analysis is done regularly. Note that the system was warming up during April and was undergoing several trial runs before the actual data could be retrieved. Hence, the data made available from May onward are considered reliable.

Figure 17 (a) shows the amount of thermal energy available for storage in BTES every day during May 2023. The irradiance values integrated over time (insolation) for each day are also shown in the figure. As evident, there were days when the daily thermal energy production was high (day 22) and negligible (days 10–11). Some days could be observed to be cloudier, especially on 19 May, indicating lower energy production. It is also apparent that the thermal energy produced was higher during the last few days, specifically between 20 May and 31 May, which is due to the availability of a higher amount of insolation. The thermal energy data exhibits a clear correlation with the corresponding insolation data. This indicates that high thermal energy corresponds to high insolation, and conversely, low thermal energy output corresponds to low insolation. However, for June, the thermal energy production was nearly consistent, except for some days (5 and 10 June). As illustrated in Figure 17 (b), unlike May, thermal energy production was considerably high for June, specifically during the second half between June 15 and 27. Here as well, the thermal energy levels for each day are proportional to the amount of insolation. It could also be seen that the average thermal energy produced during June was nearly 28 % higher as compared to the preceding month. This could be attributed to the higher amount of consistent irradiation levels during June. Also, the estimated average energy production value during May was approximately half of the maximum value recorded in the same month (on May 21), which also reflects the inconsistency in irradiation levels.

(a)

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(b)

Figure 17. Thermal energy production and insolation during (a) May and (b) June. Thick dashed lines correspond to the average thermal energy production in each month.

Figure 18 shows the insolation data available from the pyranometer on the farm, respectively, for May and June. It is obvious that the irradiance values were substantially higher during the first and last weeks of May. However, between 10 May and 20 May, the insolation was observed to be low and highly varying. For example, on 10 May, the irradiation was less than the threshold, and due to this, the pump did not operate. This is the reason why the thermal energy production was negligible that day. Similarly, on the next day (11 May), although the irradiance value crossed 200 W m^{-2} , it was not consistent enough for the pump to start operating. There was a period of low and inconsistent irradiation levels between 10 and 20 May that resulted in below-average system performance, as shown in Figure 17 (a). It should also be noted that, as illustrated in Figure 18 (b), the available solar energy was high during the same period in June. Also, the low amount of insolation on 5 and 10 June substantiates the comparatively lower thermal energy production, as shown in Figure 17 (b). All these observations clearly indicate that the system performance is continuously driven by the availability of solar irradiation.

(a)

(b)

Figure 18. Irradiance levels during the months of (a) May and (b) June.

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Figure 19. Temperature sensor data and thermal power for 10 days during (a) May 11–20 and (b) June 11–20 2023. (In the legend; T_a : ambient temperature, TT03: collector inlet temperature, TT02: collector outlet temperature, ΔT : TT02-TT03).

Having said that thermal energy production is vastly influenced by the amount of solar radiation, we found it necessary to explore the field data between 10 and 20 of May and June to understand the prime factors affecting thermal energy production. The main reason for the selection of this period was that it was during these days in May that the recorded irradiation levels were low and varying, as shown in Figure 10(a). Figure 19 shows the representative data from various sensors for May and June during the period 11–20. The data from temperature sensors TT15, TT03, and TT02 have been included in the analysis. The difference between TT02 and TT03 has been estimated together with the thermal power (kW) and shown in the figure. It could be seen that the thermal power curves were significantly driven by the corresponding values of the PVT collector outlet temperature (TT02). The ambient temperature (T_a) was also another influencing factor, as both curves followed similar variation trends. These sensor readings must be greatly influenced by the insolation. Interestingly, the corresponding field data analysis for the same period in June clearly indicated higher thermal power availability. As seen in Figure 19 (b), the thermal power values are considerably higher than in May, which is complemented by the higher levels of collector outlet temperature (TT02). A one-to-one comparison with the corresponding data from May also shows the impact of TT02 sensor values on thermal power output.

From the data made available from the farm, the total heat energy produced by the PVT system during May was estimated to be 1,807 kWh and for June it was 2,220 kWh. The comparatively lower energy production during May was due to the low amount of insolation. The field data also showed

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that the energy production reached its peak during the midday hours, typically between 11:00 h and 15:00 h when the irradiance was highest. Note that during summer, the days are longer and hence the thermal energy production on sunny days continued until around 20:00 h.

3.1.2 Electricity production analysis

The electrical production of the PVT field offsets the power consumption that the farm conventionally gets from the grid. This production could be supplied to the heat pump or any other electricity consumption point at the farm.

Given the Italian local regulations, the electricity metering was not able to be commissioned at the same time as the thermal part of the PVT system. Hence, the electrical production of the PV array was estimated through simulations developed in TRNSYS, which is a well-known component-based software that allows the modelling of dynamic systems such as solar thermal collectors, photovoltaic arrays, as well as HVAC systems. These simulations considered all the electrical and thermal performance parameters given by the manufacturer (Table 4). EPW weather files for Mirandola (Italy) were used to run the simulations with a time step of 5 min. For the months under study, the electrical production of the PV system was estimated to be 0.86 MWh and 1.11 MWh for May and June, respectively.

Table 4. Electrical characteristics of the PV module.

Parameter	Value	Unit
Max power voltage (V_{mp})	33.2	V
Max power current (I_{mp})	9.64	A
Open circuit voltage (V_{oc})	40.9	V
Short circuit current (I_{sc})	10.15	A
Module efficiency rate	19.55	%
Module aperture area (A)	1.64	m ²

3.2 Geothermal storage

In order to analyse the work of the PVT-HP-BTES system at Golinelli farm, a representative period has been chosen. The chosen period starts on 10th April 2024 and ends on 25th April 2024. The reason for this choice is the following:

From 10th to 17th April: the weather in Mirandola was very sunny, with an average irradiance during the day around 300 W m⁻² and a peak of 970 W m⁻² (Figure 20). Weather temperature in the period was high as well, with an average above 20 °C, above the commonness of April. In this period, the PVT and the solar central station were both activated and solar heat energy was injected into the borehole thermal energy storage (BTES) system.

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From 17th to 25th April, the weather temperature abruptly dropped, with reduced sun and the presence of precipitation on various days. The average weather temperature reduced to 11 °C, with low peaks down to 2.5 °C during the night. During this period, high variability of weather temperature occurred (Figure 21). In these conditions, the hallway of the piglets' building started to drop its ambient temperature, and the heat pump automatically activated to provide the necessary comfort, by extracting the heat from the borehole heat exchangers (BHEs) of the BTES and, working in hybrid mode, from the ambient air.

Figure 20. Irradiance measured in the period 10-17th April 2024.

Figure 21. Frequency distribution of weather temperature in the period 17-24th April.

The two consecutive periods are representative then of the sequence injection-extraction of the PVT-BTES-HP system.

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3.2.1 Solar energy and the BTES – 10-17th April 2024

From the monitoring system, it was possible to record the values from various sensor temperatures on the PVT and the BTES circuit (inlet/outlet) as well as the flow (average: 2530 l/h). Knowing the amount of antifreeze in the system (unavoidable for the safety of the PVT panels), it was then possible to calculate by Equation (3) the stored energy in the BTES.

$$E = \sum_{i=1}^n (T_{in,i} - T_{out,i}) \cdot Q_i \cdot c_p \cdot \rho \cdot (t_i - t_{i-1}) \quad (3)$$

Where $T_{in,i}$, $T_{out,i}$ is the fluid temperature difference between inlet and outlet of the BTES at step i (K), Q_i is the fluid flow at step i ($m^3 s^{-1}$), c_p is the fluid specific heat ($J (kg \cdot K)^{-1}$), ρ is the fluid density ($kg m^{-3}$), and $t_i - t_{i-1}$ is the reference period step for energy calculation (s).

It is worth noticing that, for environmental protection and technical reasons (reduced heat stress of the BTES pipes) the imposed maximum temperature of the injected water inside the BTES is 35 °C. After reaching such a threshold, recirculation of the fluid in the solar central station occurs.

The calculated stored energy was around 2,160 MJ, equal to 600 kWh, which is represented in cumulative form in Figure 22.

Figure 22. Energy stored in the BTES in the period 10-17 April 2024 and related inlet and outlet temperatures.

At the beginning of the period, the equivalent ground temperature in the BTES was measured around 12 °C. Since it was April, this value is the result of the several working hours of the HP for the heat extraction in the previous winter.

Using Equation (4), it was then possible to estimate the equivalent ground temperature in the BTES at the end of the solar heat injection period:

$$T_{g,f} = T_{g,i} + \frac{E}{c_g \cdot r^2 \cdot \pi \cdot H} \quad (4)$$

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where $T_{g,i}$ is the equivalent ground temperature before heat injection ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), $T_{g,f}$ is the equivalent ground temperature after heat injection ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), E is the total heat injection (J), c_g is the equivalent ground thermal capacity ($\text{J (m}^3\text{K)}^{-1}$), r is the radius of the area interested by the BTES (m), and H is the depth of the ground interested by the BTES (m).

The equivalent ground thermal capacity was previously obtained by thermal response tests (TRT) and it is around $1.7 \text{ MJ (m}^3\text{K)}^{-1}$.

Concerning the radius and depth of the area affected, the geometry of the BTES was considered. Moreover, thanks to the piezometers and the monitoring points located upwards and downwards of the BTES (with respect to groundwater flow), it was verified that the heat pulse does not go beyond the BTES geometry.

With such premises, it was expected an increase of the ground temperature in the BTES of around $0.7 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ due to solar injection.

3.3 Heat pump

3.3.1 Performance Calculations

In this section, the basic performance indicators are presented. The processing of experimental measurements was conducted using a numerical model developed in Python for the calculation of water and refrigerant properties. Utilizing the data from experimental measurements, it was feasible to calculate the thermal flows and estimate the coefficient of performance under various conditions and capacities. The thermal flows at the condenser and evaporator are identified from the measured data, as shown in Equation (5) and Equation (6).

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{Q}_{cond} &= \dot{m}_{w,cond} \cdot c_{p,w,cond} (T_{w,cond,out} - T_{w,cond,in}) = \\ &= \dot{m}_{ref,cond} \cdot (h_{ref,cond,out} - h_{ref,cond,in})\end{aligned}\quad (5)$$

where $c_{p,w,cond} [\text{kJ (kg} \cdot \text{K)}^{-1}]$ and $\dot{m}_{w,cond} [\text{kg s}^{-1}]$ are the specific heat under constant pressure and the mass flow rate of the hot source, respectively. The value of $\dot{m}_{w,cond}$ is directly calculated, given the value of $\dot{V}_{w,cond}$ and its density, which is a function of the pressure of the hot source network and the temperature.

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{Q}_{evap} &= \dot{m}_{w,evap} \cdot c_{p,w,evap} (T_{w,evap,in} - T_{w,evap,out}) = \\ &= \dot{m}_{ref,evap} \cdot (h_{ref,evap,out} - h_{ref,evap,in})\end{aligned}\quad (6)$$

where $c_{p,w,evap} [\text{kJ (kg} \cdot \text{K)}^{-1}]$ and $\dot{m}_{w,evap} [\text{kg s}^{-1}]$ represent the specific heat at constant pressure and the mass flow rate of the water at the cold side of the HP, respectively. The total power consumption of the heat pump is given by Equation (7), where \dot{w}_{aux} includes the power consumption of the water circulators, the HP's air fan, and the electrical panel.

$$\dot{w}_{HP} = \dot{w}_{comp} + \dot{w}_{aux}\quad (7)$$

where $\dot{w}_{comp} [\text{kW}]$ is the power consumed by the unit's compressor and $\dot{w}_{aux} [\text{kW}]$ represents the power consumed by the rest of the equipment (air fans, water circulators, and electrical panel).

The system's COP is calculated according to Equation (8).

$$COP = \frac{\dot{Q}_{cond}}{\dot{w}_{HP}}\quad (8)$$

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3.3.2 SCOP Testing and Calculations

The seasonal¹ performance of a heat pump serves as an indicator of its average efficiency throughout the heating and/or cooling season, considering the diverse energy demands and their fluctuations over time. For the specific application, the SCOP for the water source operation is provided, due to the availability of experimental measurements. To determine the SCOP, the standard methodology which employs spreadsheet calculations is followed, using temperature classes (T_j) and temperature period bins (bin_j) formed by the pairing of outside temperatures (T_j) and the corresponding number of annual hours (h_j). For a more detailed view, the publications of the European Commission (COMMISSION DELEGATED REGULATION (EU), 2013), DIN (DIN, 2013, 2016), and relative literature (Sieres et al., 2022) give useful information. The SCOP calculation involves defining six testing points based on temperature zones (average, warmer, or colder). In addition to these conditions, measurements are required for the bivalent point (BIV) and the operation limit temperature (TOL). At each measurement point, the HP's coefficient of performance (COP) and heat output are determined. For the case of geothermal heat pumps, these points are simplified to only a single measurement at 10 °C and a condenser outlet temperature defined by the temperature application, for which the heat pump is tested. Since the COP reflects the HP's performance under full load conditions, a method is employed to integrate part-load behaviour. According to EN 14825 (DIN, 2016) for a water-sink HP, the COP at part load conditions is given according to Equation (9).

$$COP_{PL} = COP_{DC} \cdot \frac{CR}{C_c \cdot CR + (1 - C_c)} \quad (9)$$

where the part load factor CR is the quotient of the heat demand and the heating capacity at full load and the degradation coefficient C_c is set to 0.9 (DIN, 2016). The heat demand is determined based on the outdoor temperature class T_j according to Equation (10), which represents the part load ratio at different test temperatures, defined by Equation (11).

$$\dot{Q}_h(T_j) = P_{design_h\%} \cdot \dot{Q}_h(T_{design}) \quad (10)$$

$$P_{design_h\%} = \frac{T_j - 16}{T_{design} - 16} \quad (11)$$

where $\dot{Q}_h(T_{design})$ is the nominal heat load at the design temperature T_{design} , which for average climate conditions is set to -10 °C.

In addition, for temperatures below the bivalent temperature, the thermal output of the heat pump is not sufficient to cover the load, and an additional heater is used with COP=1 by the definition. As a result, the COPs at part load conditions and the heating capacity are then suitably inter- and extrapolated to cover all temperature classes.

¹ The seasonal performance of a heat pump serves as an indicator of its average efficiency throughout the heating and/or cooling season, considering the diverse energy demands, due to the variation of ambient temperature. Ambient temperature higher than internal room temperature makes the system working for cooling, thus injecting heat in the ambient (air or ground) sink. Ambient temperature cooler than internal room temperature makes the system working for heating, thus extracting heat from the ambient (air or ground) source.

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For the overall efficiency, the ratio of the total covered heat load and total electricity consumption is identified as the average seasonal efficiency of the heat pump in active mode, as presented in Equation (12).

$$SCOP_{on} = \frac{\sum_j \dot{Q}_h(T_j)}{\sum_j \dot{W}_{HP,PL}(T_j)} \quad (12)$$

where $\dot{W}_{HP,PL}(T_j)$ is the total electricity demand at every temperature bin (T_j) determined by the COP at part load conditions. Therefore, the last step includes the calculation of the overall SCOP, in which the heat pump's consumption when deactivated must be included. This includes the electricity consumption at thermostat off mode, standby mode, crankcase heater mode, and off mode. Specifically, off mode and crankcase heater mode have zero electricity consumption, while standby mode and thermostat off mode consume 15 W each. After all, the calculation of the SCOP is determined according to Equation (13),

$$SCOP = \frac{\sum_j \dot{Q}_h(T_j)}{\frac{\sum_j \dot{Q}_h(T_j)}{SCOP_{on}} + H_{TO} \cdot E_{TO} + H_{SB} \cdot E_{SB} + H_{CK} \cdot E_{CK} + H_{OFF} \cdot E_{OFF}} \quad (13)$$

where H signifies the number of hours in a year the heat pump is in the stated operating mode. Both the number of hours H and each power consumption E is defined according to (DIN, 2016).

3.3.3 Heat Pump Performance for Varying Capacity Under Different Operation Modes

During the experimental procedure, the measurements are collected at intervals of 1 sec. Subsequently, the average values over a 20-second period are computed to align with the operational cycle of the digital capacity. Taking into consideration the analysis provided in Section 3, the heat pump's performance under different operation modes (water- and air-source) is presented. The water temperatures at the evaporator's inlet vary between 8 and 20 °C, while at the condenser, the outlet water temperature ranges from 30 to 50 °C. Figure 23 depicts the heating capacity of the heat pump and the electrical consumption as a function of the compressor's pressure ratio, while Figure 24 illustrates the COP variation with the refrigerant pressure ratio at different capacities of the compressor. Observations indicate that at 100 % compressor capacity, the available measurements are approaching pressure ratios slightly exceeding 4, leading to a heating capacity of approximately 30-32 kW, and associated electrical consumption of 6 kW_{el}, resulting in a COP of about 5. As capacities decrease, the corresponding pressure ratio also decreases, leading to a reduction in thermal load and electrical consumption. Operating at 80 % capacity results in a lower electric power demand, consequently yielding a higher COP for pressure ratios around 3. Accordingly, for the operation at 60 % and 20 %, there is a notable reduction of over 40 % and 65 % respectively in heating capacity, leading to an average COP of 4.2 for both cases, with pressure ratios around 3. Furthermore, during digital capacity operation at 20 %, where compression occurs only for 4 s within the 20-second cycle, heating capacity, and electricity consumption remain relatively constant across the entire operational spectrum.

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Figure 23. Heating capacity (left) and electric power (right) of the water-source mode in different capacities, as a function of the pressure ratio.

Figure 24. COP of the water-source mode in different capacities, as a function of the pressure ratio.

Figure 25 and Figure 26 present the same graphs for the air-source mode, showing the unit's heating capacity, electric power, and COP as the pressure ratio varies. The tests were conducted with outdoor temperatures ranging between 16-20 °C and varying the water outlet at the condenser between 30-50 °C. When the compressor operates at 100 % capacity for a pressure ratio between 3 to 6, the unit's heating capacity exceeds 30 kW. For the same operating conditions, the electric consumption was measured at about 7-12 kW_{el}, leading to a COP in the range of 3-4. It is observed that for a capacity of 80 %, the electric consumption is higher, probably due to the abrupt increase of the fan's consumption far from the design point. Under similar conditions, operation at 60 % and 20 % of full capacity exhibits a similar trend to the water option concerning the heating capacity. For electricity consumption, an increase of 1.5 – 2 kW is observed, thereby negatively impacting the COP.

Figure 25. Heating capacity (left) and electric power (right) of the air-source mode in different capacities, as a function of the pressure ratio.

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Figure 26. COP of the air-source mode in different capacities, as a function of the pressure ratio.

Finally, the heating capacity, electric power, and COP for the water-source, air-source, and hybrid mode are visually represented in Figure 27 and Figure 28. The air-source system was subjected to testing in early June when the ambient air temperature was above 15 °C. This choice of testing conditions elucidates the modest enhancement in COP observed in the hybrid operation when compared to the air-source operation. The rationale behind this lies in the fact that, under typical operational circumstances, the hybrid mode is engaged in conditions of lower air temperatures, typically ranging from approximately 5 to 10 °C. In addition, the electrical power consumed for hybrid operation is higher since both fans and water pumps are enabled, leading to increased energy consumption, and offering the highest possible thermal capacity to the building. As expected, the water-source operation leads to the highest COP performance compared to the air-source and hybrid modes, as the water temperature is higher than the corresponding air temperatures. The tests for the water-source mode present a limited pressure ratio range, as the water's hot and cold sides do not vary as significantly as the air during testing. On the other hand, despite the weak COP enhancement, hybrid operation significantly improves the heating capacity of the system, resulting in an almost 8 kW_{th} increment for the same conditions, compared to the other two modes. Based on these findings, it is evident that water source operation demonstrates a higher COP, and this highlights the importance of favouring this mode alongside the hybrid mode, to maximize the system's overall performance during the field operations.

Figure 27. Heating capacity (left) and electric power (right) in 100% compressor capacity, as a function of the pressure ratio, for the three different operation scenarios.

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Figure 28. COP in 100% compressor capacity, as a function of the pressure ratio, for the three different operation scenarios.

3.3.4 Seasonal COP Evaluation

In this section, the results of the SCOP calculations for the water source mode of the heat pump are presented, according to the European Standard EN 14825 (DIN, 2016). In the European energy labelling, SCOP for the average climate profile is mandatory and for that reason, the seasonal HP performance is identified based on that specific profile. The climate zone base for the “average” profile is the temperature distribution of Strasbourg with a total of 4,910 h for the heating season. The design temperature for the chosen climate zone is -10 °C with the heating demand adjusted to the installation's specific thermal requirements. The SCOP calculations focus on “medium” temperature applications with the part load test conditions corresponding to a single testing point at 10 °C outdoor HEX temperature and 45 °C indoor HEX temperature (DIN, 2016). The heat pump is equipped with constant flow water circulators maintaining a consistent outlet temperature for all conditions, with water flow rates determined according to EN14511 standard (DIN, 2013). The operational limit and bivalent temperature of the heat pump are set at -10°C and -9°C, respectively. The Seasonal Coefficient of Performance (SCOP) is shown in Table 5, while Figure 29 illustrates the heating load curve, the heating capacity of the HP, and the COP at part load conditions as a function of the outdoor temperature.

Table 5. SCOP for the water source mode of the heat pump.

Reference heating season		“A” Average	
Seasonal Efficiency	Reference Heating Season (EN14824), Medium temperatures (Fixed outlet 45 °C)	P _{design} , kW	33.38
		SCOP _{on}	4.09
		SCOP	4.08

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Figure 29. Heating load curve, heat capacity curve, and part load COP of the heat pump as a function of the outdoor temperature.

3.3.5 Digital Capacity Operation

Compressor capacity modulation can reduce energy consumption and control the HP's performance as was described in section 2.2. When the compressor is operating in loaded mode the compressor behaves like a standard scroll compressor providing 100 % capacity. Figure 29 illustrates the heat pump's operation with capacity control enabled (at 80 % and 60 %) over a 2-minute sample period. In Figure 29 (a), the electricity consumption of the compressor is depicted, revealing distinct cycle timing differences between the two capacity modes. During unloaded phases, electricity consumption drops to approximately 2 kW. In contrast, during loaded phases, both 80 % and 100 % capacity modes exhibit similar consumption levels, whereas the 60 % operation shows a 3-4 % reduction in electricity consumption. Figure 29 (b) showcases heating capacity variations, highlighting a notable 10 kW disparity between the 80 % and 60 % modes during compressor unloaded phases. The main reason for this variance is that longer compressor operation leads to elevating refrigerant temperatures and subsequently increased water temperatures and heating capacities. Regarding the refrigerant pressure, during the loading phase, the operating pressure ratio in 80 % capacity is higher compared to 60 % mode, leading to 2-5 bar higher pressure at the discharge line in Figure 29 (c), and 0.5 – 1.5 lower pressure at the suction in Figure 29 (d).

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Figure 30. Heat pump operation with enabled capacity control (80% and 60%) during a sample of 2 minutes: (a) Power, (b) Heating capacity, (c) Suction pressure of the compressor, (d) Discharge pressure of the compressor.

3.3.6 The hybrid geothermal-air heat pump work – 17-25th April 2024

The heat pump (HP) extracting energy from the BTES is a 35-kW hybrid heat pump able to harness heat from ground only, air only or hybrid mode. All working parameters of the machine are measured, and the target is to find an optimized solution to maximize the COP (coefficient of performance) and SPF (seasonal performance factor). For the needs of the hallway of the piglets' building, by now the HP works only in heating mode, but it was designed to reverse the circulation for cooling, too.

The imposed temperature values for the hallway and the heat pump are the following:

- The hallway must keep a minimum temperature of 14 °C.
- The outlet heating temperature from the HP to the hallway can reach a maximum of 50 °C.
- The upper limit of the cooling water temperature to deactivate the circulation pump is 10 °C.
- The ground is the preliminary source of heat for the heat pump (GEO mode).
- The standard temperature difference between the inlet and outlet from the ground side is about 3 K.
- The lower limit of the inlet ground temperature to the HP for activating the fans (HYBRID mode) is 3 °C.
- The lower limit of the inlet ground temperature to the HP for deactivating the geothermal mode is 2°C (air mode).

The heat pump system was almost able to keep the minimum temperature of the hallway during the period. The measured temperature data in the hallway are the ones present in Figure 31.

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Figure 31. Frequency distribution of temperature in the hallway in the period 17-24th April.

Comparing the frequency distributions and statistics of weather temperature and temperature in the hallway, it was possible to verify how the stability of internal temperature was satisfying (Table 6).

Table 6. Comparison of statistics on weather temperature and temperature in the hallway for the same period

	Weather temperature (°C)	Temperature in the hallway (°C)
Q0 - Minimum temperature	2.6	10.6
Q1	7.84	13.18
Q2 – Median	9.18	14.07
Q3	12.68	15.14
Q4 - Maximum temperature	22.84	18.86
Mode	8.72	13.88
Mean	10.51	14.24
Standard deviation	4.02	1.54

The result was possible by the HP work, which was activated 17.4 % of the time. The heating fluid temperature and the cumulative energy provided are presented in Figure 32.

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Figure 32. Energy provided to the hallway by the HP in the period 17-25th April 2024 and related inlet and outlet temperatures.

The extracted energy from the BHE and air was obtained by measurements, as well as the absorbed electrical energy of all devices (compressor, pumps, fans, etc.) as shown in Figure 33.

Figure 33. Comparison of energy provided to the building, electric energy absorbed, and energy extracted from the ambient (ground and air).

The provided energy to the building was around 1,200 kWh, while the electric energy absorbed was around 300 kWh, and the remaining 900 kWh were provided by the ambient. In such conditions, for the analysed period, the SPF was 4.02.

Using Equation (3) and the measurements in the HP, it was possible to divide the extracted energy into the three modes: GEO mode (only circulation in the BTES), HYBRID mode (both BTES and fans active) and AIR mode (only fans active). The result is presented in Figure 34.

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Figure 34. Energy contributions from the different HP modes: GEO, HYBRID and AIR.

The total energy extracted by the GEO Mode was about 670 kWh, while the remaining 230 kWh were extracted from the HYBRID Mode. The AIR Mode was never activated. The percentage of use in GEO Mode was then around 75 %, and the remaining 25 % was the use in HYBRID Mode.

It was finally possible to decompose the ground contribution from the air contribution inside the HYBRID Mode. The results are as follows (see Figure 35):

Figure 35. Energy contributions of BTES and fans in the HYBRID Mode.

The total energy extracted from BTES in the HYBRID mode was about 150 kWh, while 80 kWh was extracted from the air. The contribution of ground in the HYBRID mode was therefore about 65 %, while the remaining 35 % was provided by air.

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Therefore, summing the contributions of ground in GEO mode and HYBRID mode, the total contribution of the BTES was 820 kWh, while, summing the contributions of air in AIR mode and HYBRID mode, the total contributions of fans was 80 kWh. The BTES contributed then for 91 % of the total ambient source in the selected period.

Comparing the energy stored in the previous sunny period (10-17 April) and the energy extracted, the solar heat storage provided 73 % of the energy, while the remaining 27 % was furnished by the aquifer natural flow. It resulted, at the end of the cold April week (17-25th), in a slightly lower temperature of the ground with respect to the initial 12 °C, before the warm April week (10-17th April). According to Equation 4, the decrease of ground temperature in the period, due to the cumulative negative contribution, should have been $0.7 - 0.9 = -0.2$ °C. The inlet and outlet temperature values, compared with the total energy extraction from the ground are presented in Figure 36.

Figure 36. Energy extracted from the ground in both modes (GEO+HYBRID) by the HP in the period 17-25 April 2024 and related inlet and outlet temperatures.

It is worth noticing to point out that when the cooling water temperature overcomes 10 °C, the circulation pumps stop working to save energy, therefore the sensors of inlet and outlet temperature measure and record the temperature of the water in the outside pipes, not the one of the BTES.

On the other hand, thanks to the presence of antifreeze, the ground heat potential could be fully exploited and outlet temperatures of the circulation fluid reached values below zero degrees.

Finally, the activation of the air in the HYBRID mode was necessary in the coldest weather, basically during the night. This required the activation of some defrost cycles (Figure 37) to heat the fans. In total, fifty defrosting cycles, equal to 8.3 % of the total use of fans, were necessary. The defrosting of fans was mainly accomplished by an electric heater installed inside the HP, besides the fans; however, the electric absorption was limited thanks to the use of the HP itself, activated by the ground circuit, to support the electric heater. The lowest measured values of outlet water temperature in the ground circuit, below 0 °C, were mainly reached during the use of HP as a defrosting support tool.

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Figure 37. Defrosting cycle during the reference period 17-25th April 2024.

In conclusion, the average COP for the GEO, AIR, HYBRID and TOTAL work of the heat pump for the period 17-25 April 2024 is presented in Table 7.

Table 7. Average COP of the heat pump in the reference period 17-25 April 2024.

	Average COP
GROUND mode	4.67
AIR mode	No activation
HYBRID mode	3.50
TOTAL	4.34

3.4 Retrofitting of livestock building

3.4.1 Retrofitting of the hog barn

The test and the analyses of the building led to the conclusion that the most critical parts in terms of the performance of the building envelope are the windows. In fact, the two longitudinal walls were equipped with a total of 34 windows of 2.8 m x 0.8 m, with steel single-layer frames and 4 mm thick glass surfaces. These features resulted in a thermal transmittance assessed $5.9 \text{ W (m}^2\text{K)}^{-1}$. Moreover, the operational system is fully manual, so it is not possible to control the opening of the windows in a way that can limit heat losses and, more importantly, there is no way to minimize the thermal dispersions.

Therefore, the retrofitting solution focused on the replacement of the existing windows with a high-performing system, with much lower thermal transmittance, equipped with automation devices suitable to control the opening in a way that minimizes heat loss while assuring proper air exchange.

The new windows are composed of a perimeter frame in tubular stainless steel, a frame and upper counter-frame in stainless steel, with transparent infill in 16 mm thick double chamber alveolar

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polycarbonate. This solution can assure a thermal transmittance of $2 \text{ W (m}^2\text{K)}^{-1}$, i.e. around one-third of the previous situation.

Moreover, the system includes six gear motors with a limit switch for the mechanical opening, environmental sensors and actuators for the automatic openings based on temperature and air quality parameters.

3.4.2 Performance of building retrofitting

The retrofitting action carried out on the hog barn resulted in a significant improvement in the thermal performance of the building. In particular, the effect was measured in the warm season, by comparing temperature and humidity data recorded inside the barn before and after the retrofitting, under the same utilization conditions. Figure 38 shows the reduction of the indoor temperature with reference to outdoor climatic conditions and in particular, the difference between indoor and outdoor temperature was in general significantly lower after the intervention.

Then we considered relative humidity as well, so we computed the benefit in terms of THI. Specifically in August 2022, before retrofitting, the average difference between indoor THI and outdoor THI (computed at 30 min interval rate) was +1.94. Subsequently the retrofitting, such difference was -2.38. Therefore, the capacity of reduction of indoor THI was on average 4.32.

Figure 38. THI measured in the monitored indoor spaces of the nursery barn and outside.

Figure 39 shows the trend of the main environmental parameters inside the hog barn during the period under analysis, characterized by high outdoor temperatures in the initial two weeks and cold weather in the third one. The diagram shows that the natural ventilation system is suitable to keep the CO_2 concentration inside the building below the threshold of 3,000 ppm. During the period analysed, the barn was normally used to host hogs and gilts at its full capacity.

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Figure 39. Indoor parameters in the hog barn after the retrofitting.

3.5 Performances of the integrated RES system

Based on the results of hydro-geological analyses, the potential for underground thermal storage was quantified, heat dispersion due to groundwater movement was assessed, and the BTES behaviour was modelled under different operational scenarios. A depth of 30 m was deemed the most efficient solution for the thermal loads of the weaners' nursery building and, on such basis, 8 BHEs of this depth were drilled for the BTES field as the result of system dimensioning (Tinti et al. 2023). To create a Thermal Core (TC) at the centre of the BTES system for optimal thermal storage, hybrid connections were employed among the BHEs in series/parallel configurations. Heat is thus injected from the TC to the boundaries during heat storage, resulting in a higher temperature rise compared to different configurations. During the exploitation phase, heat is extracted first from the boundaries and then from the TC. The BTES field, designed to meet, consists of 4x2 BHEs arranged in a rectangular configuration, spaced 3 m apart in the North-South direction and 2 m apart in the East-West direction to optimize land use in the farmyard. The average temperature measured in a 30 m borehole in March 2023, before BTES installation, was 15.9 °C; the average temperature in 30 m boreholes measured on 10 Sep 2023, i.e. at the end of the heat injection season, was 20.5 °C. Therefore, the increase in TC temperature due to solar heat injection from May to August 2023 was 4.6 K, i.e. corresponding to the best scenario expected.

The integrated heating system of the nursery barn was analysed based on the temperature and humidity data recorded in the period 17-24 April 2024. In this week, outside temperature proved significantly low, with 9.2 °C as the average and 2.9 °C as the minimum value, thus calling for heating almost continuously the hallway through the DSHP. The temperature in the hallway was then kept above the set point of 15 °C (with a tolerance interval of 0.5 °C) for the period considered, with the temperature in the finned pipes reaching over 50 °C in several periods. The two monitored rooms,

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indicated in Figure 40, hosted weaners until 17 April and room 1 also from 24 April. However, other rooms in the building hosted weaners also in the period 18-23 April, which is why the hallway was continuously kept heated during the entire period. The heating system developed proved effective also for the control of humidity conditions in the cold season, as is witnessed by the THI trends in the weaners' rooms, that is substantially kept below the alert threshold of 75.

Figure 40. THI measured in the monitored indoor spaces of the nursery barn and outside.

The geothermal source was always used during the working time of the heating system and the circulation through the BHEs produced a temperature increase of up to 9.1 K in the cold side of the DSHP. The average temperature difference between the flows from and to BTES during the period analysed, i.e. the effect of the heat extraction was 3.0 K, corresponding to an average thermal power of 15.3 kW. The exploitation of the geothermal storage thus allowed to achieve high efficiency in the DSHP, as shown by the ratio of the heating capacity and the electric power used, reported in Figure 27. The resulting coefficient of performance (COP) is represented as well in the same diagram with hourly intervals, and the average COP in the studied period was 4.34. The COP of the DSHP when operating only in geo-source mode increased to 4.67.

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4 TESTING AND MONITORING OF THE INSTALLED SOLUTIONS IN THE LVAT FARM

The RES4LIVE interventions on the LVAT farm suffered from several delays with regard to their installation and their operational readiness. As a result, most systems could not be fully monitored before November 2023. This mainly affects the PVT system, for which it was not possible to monitor a full year during the project duration. The other systems are either more seasonally independent (the BioCNG upgrade plant and the CNG tractor) or are only relevant during summer (the tube ventilation and cooling system), so that they are not considerably impacted by the delay.

4.1 Biomethane upgrading plant and filling station

A key parameter that needs to be monitored in the process of upgrading biogas to compressed natural gas (BioCNG) is the CH₄ content. Since there is only one vehicle that uses the CNG, the BioCNG upgrade plant is used discontinuously, and it is required to reach a CH₄ content of at least 94 % after the single-stage membrane for the CNG to be compressed and stored as fuel. It is possible to acquire CH₄ contents up to 97 % with the single-stage membrane, as shown in Figure 41. The average duration to reach a methane content of 94 % after starting the plant is 26.78 minutes. The stored CNG then has an average methane content of 96.75 %.

Figure 41. Methane sensor results in the BioCNG upgrade plant during a week in March 2024.

The next important aspect of the biogas upgrade and purification process is the energy demand from the dual-use compressor. It is the most relevant energy consumer of the BioCNG upgrade plant and therefore is a crucial part of the success of the operation. The cumulative energy consumption during the last year of RES4LIVE is depicted in Figure 42. The gaps in the graph show that there were some recurrent issues with data transfer to the cloud storage, but it also shows that the internal data was not lost and is useable to assess the overall energy consumption during the project period.

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Figure 42. Cumulative energy consumption of the BioCNG upgrade plant during the last year of RES4LIVE.

During the last year of RES4LIVE, the energy consumption of the BioCNG upgrade plant amounted to 1,999.7 kWh, which corresponds to 500 operation hours at an energy usage of 4 kWh h⁻¹. This is enough to produce 3 kg h⁻¹ CNG with a methane content of 95 %. The processing of the biogas comes with a specific energy consumption of 0.94 kWh_{el} Nm⁻³ BioCNG.

Due to only a single vehicle using the CNG, the utilization of the BioCNG upgrade plant was only about 6 % of the time during the last year of RES4LIVE. Considering that the plant was a prototype with too little production capacity to be economically feasible even at higher utilization, it is a logical step that the newer commercially available variants of the plant come with a higher minimum capacity for biogas purification. The next generation comes with an increased purification capacity by factor 3.5 (35 Nm³ h⁻¹), but only at an increase of energy demand by factor 3.05, indicating the potential for increased energy effectiveness with larger scales.

4.2 Tractor refit for CNG use

A former diesel tractor was retrofitted for usage of the CNG from the BioCNG upgrade plant. For monitoring the performance of the CNG engine, a telemetry data logger was intended to be used. Due to incomprehensible reasons, it was not possible to connect to the data logger in the tractor at the LVAT pilot farm from CRMT in France. Only in April 2024, it was found that the UMTS technology that was the base for data transfer and that had worked during the testing in France was no longer available in Germany since 2022. Despite efforts that included the manufacturer of the data logger, the data could not be retrieved. A new solution for the telemetry was implemented, but after the installation, the tractor broke down to an unrelated gearbox damage that could not yet be repaired to date. As a result, the tractor's performance can only be assessed based on test runs at CRMT in France during and after the retrofit.

The power level of the tractor could be maintained with the refit, at 56 kW. At the same time, the emissions could be improved from the original level stage II to at least stage III B. Regarding fuel consumption, 1 kg BioCNG replaces between 1 and 1.25 L of diesel fuel and allows running the

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tractor completely with fuel from renewable sources. The consumption amounts to approximately 2 kg BioCNG h⁻¹.

4.3 PVT system and heat recovery system

The PVT system at the LVAT pilot farm has been in operation since November 2023. While the installation was completed in September 2023, connecting the system to the farm grid took some more time. The energy production during the last eleven months of RES4LIVE is shown in Figure 43.

Figure 43. Cumulative energy production of the PVT system at the LVAT pilot farm during the last eleven months of RES4LIVE.

The total thermal energy production during that period amounted to 8,177.4 kWh, and the total electrical energy production came in at 3,002.4 kWh. For the assessment of a full year the last month is missing, but based on the measured data a statistical method can be used to estimate a full year's production. When applying a linear regression model with a sine curve approach, the predicted values for a full year of thermal and electrical energy production with the LVAT's PVT system amount to 8,633.4 kWh and 3,164.5 kWh, respectively.

The same sine curve approach had to be applied to the irradiation monitoring (see Figure 44). Here it was not just one month missing, but a malfunction of the irradiation sensor during the spring of 2024 made it necessary to replace that sensor, which took almost three months to do. The available data from four months during winter and four months during summer could be used to validate the estimation with the sine curve approach. In winter, the approach led to an overestimation of the irradiation by 6.7 %, while the fit in summer was better with an overestimation of only 0.4 % compared to the measured data. Overall, the result was considered usable for calculating the effectiveness of the PVT system.

The electrical energy can be used to power various devices in the daily operation of the LVAT, but synergies are expected with the tube ventilation and cooling system that is required to be used in the welfare barn under conditions that are also well suited for photovoltaic energy production: hot

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afternoons with lots of sunshine and therefore irradiation. The thermal energy that is produced at the same time is transferred to a 1,500 L short-term heat storage, allowing to use of pre-heated water in the e-boiler that prepares hot water for the cleaning and disinfection of the milking systems. This saves electrical energy to heat water, which otherwise would be provided by the LVAT's combined heat and power plant (CHP) or from the national power grid.

Figure 44. Measured and predicted irradiation at the LVAT pilot farm during the last year of RES4LIVE.

The results of the efficiency assessment for the PVT system can be found in Table 8.

Table 8. PVT system conversion efficiency at the LVAT farm.

Period	Solar irradiance		PVT production		Conversion efficiency (%)		
	kWh/m ²	kWh	kWh _{el}	kWh _{th}	electrical	thermal	
November 2023							
Whole year	– October 2024, missing data predicted	1,092.1	60,544.4	3,164.5	8,633.4	6.80	14.26
Winter	November 2023 – February 2024	120.8	6,015.0	209.0	315.0	4.06	5.24
Summer	June 2024 – September 2024	592.3	29,487.2	2,149.0	5,102.5	8.52	17.30

4.4 Barn ventilation and cooling system

The barn ventilation and cooling system took until spring 2024 to work as intended. Data from the environmental sensors that control the system will be covered in section 2.3.5. In short, the fans will start running between 40 % to 100 % of volume flow in the range from 15 °C to 19 °C barn temperature, while the cooling pads join in at 24 °C. The energy consumption was monitored

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separately for both parts of the system. Occasionally there are gaps in the data that are caused by power outages in the dairy welfare barn at the LVAT. While most systems in that barn are restarted automatically in that case, the data monitoring requires a manual restart, and depending on the environmental conditions it sometimes takes a while to notice the shutdown of the data loggers. This also led to implausible data when the cooling system was shown as running while the fans were not, which by the settings of the system is impossible. This occurred during 20 days in the measuring period. In these cases, it can be deduced that based on the system settings the fans are also running at full volume flow, hence this missing data could be inserted retrospectively and is already included in Figure 45.

Figure 45. Energy consumption as measured from the tube ventilation and cooling system at the LVAT pilot farm during the 2024 summer season.

The measured energy consumption amounts for the cooling parts of the system and the ventilators were in total 916.8 kWh and 3,054.28 kWh, respectively. Adding the energy requirements for the fans running at maximum volume flow during the aforementioned data inconsistencies increases the energy consumption from the ventilation part of the system by around 14.5 % or roughly 450 kWh.

4.5 Sensors and smart control

Sensors for environmental traits such as temperature and relative humidity as well as gas concentrations for carbon dioxide and ammonia were installed in the LVAT's welfare dairy barn. Since humidity usually is not at the limit in the temperate climate zone, temperature is the main trait to be used in the barn climate control system. Similarly, both gases are not expected to accumulate towards hazardous concentrations in naturally ventilated barns; therefore, they are not relevant towards barn climate control but could be used for estimation of the gaseous emissions from the barn.

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The ammonia sensors that were initially considered for RES4LIVE turned out to be unsuited for dairy barns, where the relatively low concentrations could not be detected reliably. During the project, they therefore were replaced with a photoacoustic gas monitor system (Picarro G2509) that is used by ATB in barn climate measurement campaigns and known to work properly in dairy barn conditions. Figure 46 and Figure 47 show gas concentration measurements during one week in winter (a) and summer (b) each for carbon dioxide and ammonia, respectively.

Figure 46. CO₂ concentrations in the LVAT welfare barn during one week in the 2024 winter (a) and summer (b) seasons.

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Figure 47. NH_3 concentrations in the LVAT welfare barn during one week in the 2024 winter (a) and summer (b) seasons.

For both gases, concentrations are a bit higher in winter, which can be attributed to the lower air exchange rates in winter due to the use of windbreak curtains.

In Figure 48 and Figure 49, the temperature and humidity conditions during example weeks in winter (a) and summer (b) are depicted, respectively. While the winter week is not affected by the tube ventilation and cooling system (Figure 48(a)), the summer week (Figure 48(b) and Figure 49(b)) indicate the influence of the injection of pre-cooled air, slowing down the barn temperature increase and increasing relative humidity during peak times from noon to afternoon.

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Figure 48. Barn temperature in the LVAT welfare barn during one week in the 2024 winter (a) and summer (b) seasons.

It turned out that the cooling effect is difficult to monitor with the temperature sensors that are mounted 2.7 m above ground and therefore above the animal zone. Due to the behaviour of dairy cattle, the animal zone is mostly unsuited for the placement of sensors. Individual temperature measurements with handheld devices in the animal zone showed temperature drops of up to 5 K when the cooling system was active. The size of the cooling effect depends on the environmental conditions as well as on the distance to the injection point of the pre-cooled air. More expensive solutions with better-insulated airflow tubes could improve the cooling effect further away from the injection point.

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Figure 49. Relative humidity in the LVAT welfare barn during one week in the 2024 winter (a) and summer (b) seasons.

The smart control starts turning on the ventilation fans once the barn temperature reaches 15 °C. At that temperature, the fans run at a capacity of 40 %, which is increased up to 100 % capacity in two steps until the barn temperature is at 19 °C. The pre-cooled air from the cooling pads is added to the mix once the barn temperature reaches 24 °C.

4.6 Connections between the installed (and existing) systems at the LVAT pilot farm

The interesting part of implementing RES is to analyze how they go together and complement each other, especially in the case of the LVAT where not only energy sources have been installed, but also a system that consumes more energy, with the tube ventilation and cooling system. An overview of

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energy supply and demand at the LVAT during an energy-intense period in high summer is given in Figure 50 (a) and (b) below.

(a)

(b)

Figure 50. Energy production and consumption of the RES at the dairy operation of the LVAT farm, including energy production from the combined heat and power plant (CHP) (a) and with a focus on comparing the PVT system with tube ventilation and cooling system during the summer season (b).

Figure 50 (a) shows the baseline for energy demand between 60 and 80 kWh in the dairy operation at the LVAT and also shows that, aside from a few peaks, this is mostly covered by the already previously existing CHP running with biogas from the biogas plant. The thermal energy produced in the PVT system covers about 20 % of the CHP energy during the peak times around noon. Figure 50 (b) also shows well the earlier shutdown of thermal energy production, sometimes even before noon, compared to electrical energy production. As soon as the short-term heat storage with a volume of 1,500 L is filled, no more thermal energy is produced, while the production of photovoltaic

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electricity continues ideally until sunset. During the day under these conditions, the PVT system provides around 2 kW of power.

When compared to the energy consumer among the RES4LIVE interventions, the tube ventilation and cooling system, it becomes obvious that the demand for ventilation extends beyond the sunshine duration of the day. Especially during summer, there is a 24-hour demand for ventilation to provide sufficient air exchange in the welfare barn. This base load, therefore, should not be covered by a PVT system, instead, this is a task for the CHP. The cooling part on the other hand is usually only necessary during the daytime and also has an additional power requirement in the magnitude of electrical power the PVT system can provide. This is a clear synergy, but this requires careful prior planning on both parts to find the correct size of both systems.

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5 TESTING AND MONITORING OF THE INSTALLED SOLUTIONS IN THE AUA FARM

Although the integrated RES at the AUA poultry farm became fully operational in May 2023 with the arrival of a new batch of laying hens, each system has been monitored from day one of its commissioning to ensure proper installation, prevent malfunctions, and gain preliminary insights into their performance.

5.1 Sensors and smart control system

In the AUA poultry farm, the control system is installed in both compartments – pullets and hens’ rooms – and its main goal is:

- The efficient control of the heat pump
- Control of the ventilation through the heat pump control system
- Energy-intensive task scheduling through demand forecasting and solar generation forecasting

The sensory equipment is connected via a gateway to a cloud platform, where data from energy meters, and environmental sensors, as well as the Libelium weather station, are collected. The energy meters are used to monitor (i) the overall poultry house consumption, and (ii) the production of the PVs. Based on the farm’s needs, the following sensors were deemed necessary for monitoring the indoor space environment of each room: (i) three for Temperature and Relative humidity, (ii) one for CO₂ concentration, and (iii) one for NH₃ concentration, as shown in Figure 51.

Figure 51. Environmental sensors and gateway at the AUA farm.

It has to be noted that even though the body of the sensors TH2 and TH6 are located at the front, their probes have been placed in the middle part of the cages. Additionally, during the first month of the heat pump’s operation, manual temperature and relative humidity measurements took place

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with high precision/ resolution equipment² in order to identify which sensor provides the most reliable readings. After cross-checking, TH5 and TH3 values were found to be closer to the manual measurements.

Representative monitored data of the environmental sensors of the hens' room during March 2024 are presented in Figure 52 to Figure 55 below. The indoor temperature (Figure 52) of the hens' room fluctuates around the set point temperature, 20 °C (see section 2.4.3).

Figure 52. Temperature inside the AUA hens' room.

At this point, the dehumidification mode, though tested, has not been activated yet. This is the reason why the relative humidity inside the hens' room is exceeding the set range (40-60 %), as shown in Figure 53.

Figure 53. Relative humidity inside the AUA hens' room.

CO₂ and NH₃ concentrations are shown in Figure 54 and Figure 55, respectively. NH₃ is maintained well below the upper limit, while the CO₂ concentration is shown to increase for the first twenty days of a malfunction of the exhaust fan that was repaired on 20/03.

² DOSTMANN electronics P700 Universal: <https://dostmann-electronic.de/product/p700-universal-thermometer-1-channel.html>

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Figure 54. Carbon dioxide concentration inside the AUA hens' room.

Figure 55. Ammonia concentration inside the AUA hens' room.

In mid-April 2023, a new pullet batch arrived. Representative monitored data of the environmental sensors of the pullets' room in April 2024 in the Figures below. The 15th of April 2024 marks the arrival of a new batch with the activation of heating mode (Figure 56), and the increase in CO2 concentration (Figure 57).

Figure 56. Temperature inside the AUA pullets' room.

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Figure 57. Carbon dioxide humidity inside the AUA pullets' room.

In Figure 58 and Figure 59 below, relative humidity and NH₃ concentration readings for April 2024 are presented, respectively.

Figure 58. Relative humidity inside the AUA pullets' room.

Figure 59. Ammonia concentration inside the AUA pullets' room.

While the energy meter incorporated in the smart control system provides an overview of a number of factors (Figure 60), the aggregated energy use (Figure 61) is the monitored value of most interest.

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Figure 60. Energy meter's features.

Figure 61. Aggregated energy use of the AUA poultry house.

5.2 PV system

The 9 kWp photovoltaic (PV) system installed on the AUA pilot farm has been operational since 12/2021, but the measurements have been logged on the cloud since 05/2023³. Indicative results of the aggregated energy produced by the installed PV system during July 2023 (Figure 62) and April 2024 (Figure 63) are presented below.

³ Earlier measurements (from 01/2022) are available on inverter's manufacturer web app.

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Figure 62. Aggregated energy production of the AUA PV system in July 2023.

Figure 63. Aggregated energy production of the AUA PV system in April 2024.

The total energy produced was 934 kWh and 773 kWh in July '23 and April '24, respectively, as recorded by the installed inverter. Since there is no reference system, the acquired data are compared to the simulation results of the PVGIS tool⁴ (Figure 64). Considering factors such as shading⁵ and dust, as well as systems losses⁶ and ageing, this deviation is considered reasonable.

⁴ Since there is no reference system, the acquired data were compared with the simulation results of the PVGIS tool. PVGIS estimates the potential PV production based on historical solar radiation data and system parameters. However, real-world production depends on factors like module degradation, dirt accumulation, shading, and system losses, as described in D4.3 as well. Taking these into account, the deviation between theoretical PVGIS estimates and monitored energy production for July '23 (1,359.91 kWh vs. 934 kWh) and April '24 (1,126.67 kWh vs. 773 kWh) is considered adequate and reasonable, indicating smooth system operation during different periods, which is the overall objective of D4.3. Regarding point (a), a more detailed examination of the inverter's logs was carried out. Considering the inverter's minimum DC voltage threshold (80 V), voltage drops occurred during these periods, accounting for less than 2% of the time in April and 7% in July (not considering early morning or late evening hours). For this reason, their overall impact is evaluated as quite small.

⁵ A 15-20 % of the total area is covered during a large part of the year by the nearby trees.

⁶ PVGIS considers a 14 %.

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Figure 64. Indicative electrical energy production for a 9 kWp PV system (PVGIS).

From preliminary data processing between May 2023 and April 2024 (12 months), the PV electricity production covers between 20.20 % and 68.13 % of the total energy needs on a monthly basis, and 25.25% yearly. A characteristic energy use profile for a 3-day period in July 2023 (23-25/07/2023) is presented in Figure 65. No storage system is included, so when the PV production exceeds the energy needs of the facility - though not common - the nearby auxiliary buildings are supplied with electricity.

Figure 65. Energy use profiles for a 3-day period in July 2023.

5.3 Heat pump and ventilation

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As mentioned above, the AUA heat pump for controlling the indoor environment of the poultry house by supplying the necessary heating, cooling, and dehumidifying loads, became operational in May 2023. As shown in Figure 66, the cloud platform provides a number of control and operation monitoring parameters.

Figure 66. Heat pump control and operation parameters available on the cloud platform.

The heat pump's operation is controlled primarily by its Programmable Logic Controller (PLC), which is fed with real-time data from the smart control systems. The temperature and relative humidity set points for each room are defined via the cloud platform as well (Figure 67).

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Control

Athens Farm Gateway

Heat Pump Gateway: Athens Farm Gateway

You can perform live actions. Gateway is online.

Warning: All actions directly affect the heatpump.

Heat Pump

Status

✎ Edit
📄 Update
✕ Cancel

Status	Value
Air Setpoint chamber 2	210
Air Setpoint chamber 1	210
On Chamber 1	ON
On Chamber 2	ON
Remote Start/Stop Command	ON

Figure 67. Setpoints for temperature on the cloud platform

The main parameters of the heat pump operation can be monitored in real-time online, as well as exported in .png and .csv format (Figure 68).

📄 Export to PNG
Export CSV in ▾

UTC

Athens (GMT+3)

Figure 68. Data export options from the cloud.

The figures below show indicative heat pump parameters that allow the assessment of the unit's proper operation and further data processing and calculations. The period between 25/07 and 28/07/2023 has been selected to showcase the activation of the heat pump's compressor (Figure 69), and the refrigerant's low and high pressures (Figure 70).

Figure 69. Compressor ON, between 25/07 and 28/07/2023.

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Figure 70. Refrigerant low (top) and high (bottom) pressure (in bar), between 25/07 and 28/07/2023.

Due to technical difficulties, the heat pump’s power consumption was added to the cloud a bit later. The power consumption for the period between 01/12 and 03/12/2023 is presented in Figure 71 below.

Figure 71. Heat pump power consumption (in kW), between 01/12 and 03/12/2023.

For previous periods, the heat pump’s power consumption can be calculated with acceptable accuracy based on the refrigerant’s pressures, and the compressor’s polynomials provided by the manufacturer. The same holds true for other performance indicators (e.g., heating/ cooling capacity, COP). Indicative results on indoor temperature variation and HP performance between the 20th and 30th of July 2023 are presented in Figure 72 below, evaluating HP’s performance as satisfactory.

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Figure 72. Temperatures variation and HP performance between 20-30/07/2023.

During the monitoring period presented (July 20–30, 2023), the heat pump operated exclusively in cooling mode. The summer of 2023 was among the warmest in recent years in Greece, with outdoor temperatures reaching up to 46°C. Despite the extreme conditions, the heat pump effectively maintained the indoor temperature within the setpoint range of $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, which is considered the upper thermal comfort limit for laying hens. The system was programmed to shut off when the indoor temperature dropped to 23°C, but due to high thermal loads, this was not achievable during the monitoring period. Nevertheless, even under peak outdoor temperatures, the indoor temperature did not exceed 30°C. The HP provided the expected cooling loads, with a COP exceeding 2 for most of the monitoring period. To represent a real-world efficiency rating over the 30-day period, the seasonal cooling output was divided by the seasonal energy input, resulting in a CSPF of 2.42. Given the specific application, presenting the actual heat pump performance was considered more useful and practical than using the Seasonal Energy Efficiency Ratio (SEER), which is based on standardized lab conditions.

Finally, additional parameters concerning the fans' operation, such as the unit's fan capacity (Figure 73) allow the estimation of the energy use profile for the rest of the system's components.

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Figure 73. Units' fan capacity (%), between 25/07 and 28/07/2023.

5.4 LED system

The LED system is not connected to the rest of the developed smart control system, though there is the possibility of its integration. The LEDs are both controlled and monitored via the manufacturer's online application (Figure 74).

Figure 74. LED manufacturer's application interface.

Via this application is possible to monitor the hourly, daily, weekly, and yearly consumption (Figure 75), which is, more or less, constant because of the fixed daily program. Based on the installed capacity ($W m^{-1}$), and the defined intensity and hours of operation, the initially estimated value on a daily basis (1.03 kWh) agrees with that of the application's readings⁷.

⁷ The reason behind the difference observed between the estimated and measured data for May 2024 is due to (i) damages parts of LEDs, and (ii) power outages that took place during this month.

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Figure 75. LED consumption as shown in the manufacturer's application.

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6 CONCLUSIONS

WP4 focused on the implementation and testing of solutions in pilot farms. Previous deliverables, D4.1 and D4.2, covered the design and preparation of these solutions, followed by their installation on the pilot farms. This D4.3, presented the outcomes from monitoring the interventions, specifically their performance and efficiency. After a brief introduction, detailed key metrics for each intervention in the four pilot farms are presented. The findings from this deliverable contributed to subsequent Tasks in other work packages, such as T5.1 (Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform) and T6.5 (Inventory of best practices of RES4LIVE in livestock farms).

The results demonstrate that most of the RES installations at the pilot farms operate efficiently, significantly reducing or fully replacing the use of fossil fuels across various livestock operations. In particular, the heat pumps and PVT systems have shown strong performance, meeting expected energy efficiency targets. A promising solution is the BioCNG upgrade plant, especially when paired with CNG-powered vehicles; however, its practical viability depends on scaling the system to a size that ensures economic feasibility. Achieving this requires careful planning and precise dimensioning of RES installations to align with the specific energy demands and operational requirements of each farm. Tailoring the technology to these needs is critical for optimizing performance and ensuring long-term sustainability.